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Project roles across career stages in the academic workforce may be misaligned with career utility¹

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Introduction

Team based project organization plays a critical role in the advancement of scientific knowledge, and the allocation of research work within teams affects the training of early career researchers (postdoctoral researchers, students; ECRs) and their ability to pursue their desired scientific career (Robinson-Garcia et al., 2020). Within research teams, there are still established hierarchies of research tasks, where some forms of work carry greater prestige and opportunity for advancement. While a majority of new doctorate holders rate academia as their top choice for a post-PhD career (Woolston, 2019) an increasing number of recent graduates find the pathway inaccessible (Cyranski et al., 2011; Doctorate Recipients from U.S. Universities: 2018, 2019; Schillebeeckx et al., 2013). This disconnect may be exacerbated by the division of labor on research teams where the supporting research roles that ECRs occupy may not be aligned with priorities for hiring and promotion decisions (Leahey et al., 2010; Milojević et al., 2018; Robinson-Garcia et al., 2020). In addition, the emphasis on peer-reviewed publication may serve to undervalue service and teaching activities that may be disconnected from their research work. While the devaluation of supporting research work is known, the extent to which scientists' strategic decisions about their next career steps are affected by their ability to dedicate time to more prestigious research tasks is unknown. Are the tasks that researchers, particularly Early Career Researchers, aligned with what they value most and with what they feel will advance their career within in the academy?

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Here we conduct a survey of academic scientists in the United States about their usual and desired roles on project teams, and the extent to which they see their current work contributing to their desired career. The respondents' perceptions of the roles that they have performed during their own work will shed light on the extent to which researcher expectations and career decisions are affected by their positioning on project teams and seniority. Understanding the distribution of labor on research teams can inform policy decisions to correctly incentivise the types of work that will advance scientific innovation and provide opportunities for early career researchers.

Methods

To compose a sampling frame, we identified a set of peer-reviewed scientific papers in Clarivate's Web of Science that were published in the last two years (2019 through 2021) with the subject assigned as biology, clinical medicine, or biomedical research according to the paper disciplinary classification that was developed for the National Science Foundation (K. Hamilton, 2003). We focus on these fields due to their embrace of team-based science (Alberts, 2012). The final contact list contained 138,387 unique researchers with email addresses and affiliations in the United States. We emailed each author a link to participate in the survey and a request to forward the survey and message to collaborators who are currently or who had been graduate students or postdocs in the past two years.

We prepared a questionnaire that asks researchers in different career positions to rank the prominence of 14 different research-related tasks as defined by the CRediT taxonomy with regard to 4 different criteria: Time (time spent performing the task), Credit (number of papers one received co-author credit for by performing the task), Career (perceived usefulness of the task to desired career), and Value (perceived value of the task to identity as a scientist). After parsing the survey responses, we were able to calculate the proportion of researchers who rank each of the 14 CRediT tasks among their top three tasks in terms of these four categories. We then compared rankings between categories by calculating the difference in these proportions. For instance, if 70% of postdoctoral researchers rank Funding Acquisition among their top 3 tasks for Career utility, but only 30% report that they spend substantial Time on this task, then a difference of 40 is reported. We call this an alignment score, and it allows us to discern when a task is highly ranked in one category but not in the other. An alignment score near 0 indicates that tasks are ranked similarly in both categories.

Results

Our survey had a response rate of 3.3% (n=4570) from the direct link; 516 additional participants reached the survey from the anonymous link, meaning that they had been forwarded the survey by a collaborator. This amounts to a sum of 5086 total responses, with an 83% completion rate

Current setting & Desired career

We find that researchers aim to stay in the same setting as their current position (Figure 1). Within academic research, a higher proportion of respondents from more senior research positions indicate that they will target research focused universities (labelled R1, or very high research activity, in the Carnegie Classification) during their job search compared to ECRs, possibly reflecting as researchers reach more senior positions, their resolution to stay in academic research strengthens. Conversely, researchers who are in training roles, such as student appointments or postdoctoral positions, indicate a desire to target roles outside academic research, most commonly government, teaching universities, and medical institutions (Figure 1). This may reflect either an increased openness to pursuing non-academic roles among

ECRs, or a tacit acknowledgement that there is a more limited supply of positions in research-intensive academia than in other settings.

Figure 1: Current and desired career settings. The position of researchers entering or currently on the job market (left side), connected by a line to their desired setting (right side). The sizes of each box and the width of connecting flows between the boxes is proportional to the number of researchers either currently in or desirous of each position.

Project Roles

In general, we find that Funding Acquisition and Conceptualization are perceived as important for respondents' Careers, however only administrators and researchers in senior academic positions report spending a high proportion of their Time on these tasks. We also observed instances in which some of the 14 research-related tasks showed misalignment between survey categories (see Methods). For example, we asked respondents about which tasks are important to their Career and which tasks they spend the most Time performing. In this context, Funding Acquisition and Conceptualization both appear as tasks with a large misalignment for ECRs, particularly postdocs (Figure 2). This means that a large proportion of ECRs indicate that these tasks are highly important for their career, while relatively few respondents report spending significant time on these activities. On the other hand, Writing the Original Draft, Formal Analysis, and Investigation are roles that a larger proportion of ECRs report spending considerable time on, while few perceive them as highly important for career advancement. The same is true for more senior researchers and tasks such as Writing – review and editing, and Supervision: they spend a high proportion of their time on these tasks, but do not view them as useful for their career, likely because a shift from a more active role in research to a mentorship role coincides with career advancement.

Figure 2: Alignment score between Career importance and Time spent performing each task. Blue indicates that task is often ranked highly for Career importance and not for Time spent performing. Red indicates that the task is often ranked highly for Time spent performing and not for Career importance.

Discussion & Conclusion

This study highlights the varied careers desired by biology and biomedical researchers, many of which remain the traditional tenure-track faculty position. This study also speaks to the need for researchers to have flexibility and access to project roles that will best prepare them for their desired career. However, the gap between the desired project roles and the roles they indicate occupy the majority of their time suggests that the current pipeline of research work is still tailored toward the types of work required by tenure track faculty positions, whether or not those roles are available or desired by researchers.

We will also use these data to examine how individual researcher confidence for achieving their desired career is associated with the extent that their desired roles overlap with their actual roles on project teams. We will also explore gender differences in project roles and the alignment of current and desired project roles.

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